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ASSESSMENT OF READINESS TO SHIFT FROM PLASTIC CARRIER BAGS – AN ANALYSIS OF GREEN ALTERNATIVES AMONG PUNE RETAILERS

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ABSTRACT

Maharashtra has banned plastic carrier bags since 2010. Irrespective of the government ban and the tremendous negative environmental and health damages, plastic bags are still dominating the state's markets, street corners, drainage system, landfills and particularly the citizens' hearts. People feel it's the most convenient way to deliver or carry their stuffs. In this research paper, qualitative and quantitative methodology has been used to analyze researcher's ideas based on literature review and survey. The paper focuses on the assessment of the demand and the readiness of the retailers and consumers to shift to other biodegradable alternatives. The research study could be applied to generate alternate income opportunity for local underprivileged women.

Keywords : *Plastic-free, readiness, shift, awareness, sustainable, bio-degradable alternatives, eco-friendly, environmental pollution.*

Background :

Oblivious to the after-effects of plastic bags, every customer is easily carried away by the benefits it offers, such as convenience, flexibility, lightness, durability, water-resistance, good insulation and inexpensive nature etc. On one hand, plastic bags have made our life easier and on the other hand, its current level of usage, physical pollution and production and disposal have unfortunately created serious environmental damage realized by the scientists within the last 30 years.

The diversity of polymers and the versatility of their properties are utilized to make many types of products that bring medical and technological advances, energy savings and numerous other societal benefits (Andrady & Neal 2009). As a result, about 280 million tons

of plastic are produced annually in the world (Shaw and Sahni2014) for the manufacturing of products such as storage containers, packaging material, or even automobiles. Almost all aspects of daily life involve plastics, in transport, telecommunications, clothing, footwear and as packaging materials that facilitate the transport of a wide range of food, drink and other goods. There is considerable potential for new applications of plastics that will bring benefits in the future, for example as novel medical applications, in the generation of renewable energy and by reducing energy used in transport (Andrady& Neal 2009).

Majority of the disposable and short-lived products are discarded within one year of their manufacture. Only in the USA , approximately 48 million ton of plastic are generated each year (Sarker et al. 2012b). Almost one third of the plastic produced is used to manufacture single-use plastics (Di Gregorio 2012) such as coffee cup lids, stirrers, or straws. Annually, more than 35 million plastic bottles and 500 billion plastic bags are used by consumers, many of which end up in our oceans and along our beaches (What a Waste 2010).

The percentage of plastics that make up the total municipal solid waste has risen 12 % over the last four decades (EPA 2014). The municipal solid waste generated daily in the city of Pune has been estimated at 1300 to 1400 metric tons (approximate generation per capita per day is 500 grams)(Akolkar, A.B., 2005)

Around 10 per cent by weight of the municipal waste stream is plastic (Barnes et al. 2009) Out of this, around 1900 MT is recyclables, of which just 700 MT is recycled daily. The rest 1200 MT (mainly plastic) add to the untreated waste. A plastic bag has been one of the most popular usages of this material. The cumulative effects of individual shoppers using one or two plastic shopping bags a day adds up to between 500 billion and one trillion used and discarded every year on a global scale.

The characteristics that have made plastic bags so commercially successful and omnipresent—namely their light weight and durability—have also contributed to their spread in the environment. The chemical bonds between the molecules that comprise plastic not only make them resilient, but also donot allow it to biodegrade in nature (Shaw and Sahni2014). It can only photodegrade into smaller toxic particles and that too can take centuries.

Majority bags are not recycled and they end up into landfill and garbage heaps after they are used and create huge environmental danger. They clog up gutters and drains causing water

and sewage to overflow and become the breeding grounds of germs and bacteria that cause diseases

Once littered, plastic bags fly and find their way to our streets, parks, gardens, trees and into our waterways which besides being ugly, can kill birds, small mammals and other creatures by consumption and creating visual problems.

Water bodies specially the ocean gyres found in the Atlantic, Pacific, and Indian Oceans, are becoming the final destination for these non-biodegradable polymers (NOAA 2008). As a result of plastic waste, Earth's ocean and freshwater biodiversity and ecosystems are being negatively affected. Unable to pass the debris that forms a solid mass, a "plastic rock" in their stomachs over time, the animals slowly starve to death.. Others become entangled in plastic bags and drown. Due to ingestion or entanglement in plastic debris, over 270 species and 100,000 whales, turtles, fish, seabirds, and mammals, have experienced impaired movement, starvation, or death (Laist 1997; Wabnitz and Nichols 2010). (The World Wide Fund for Nature) These observations alone indicate that our current use of plastics is not sustainable

Plastic production is also not at all sustainable. Around 4 per cent of world oil and gas production, a non-renewable resource, is used as feedstock for plastics and a further 3–4% is expended to provide energy for their manufacture. Plastic carry bags are manufactured using organic and inorganic additives like colorants and pigments, plasticizers, antioxidants, stabilizers and metals. Many such additives are used in large quantities and in a wide range of products (Meeker et al. 2009). Colorants and pigments are industrial anodynes which are used to give bright color to plastic carry bags. Some of these are carcinogenic and likely to contaminate food stuffs, if packed in these carry bags. Toxic metals like cadmium and lead when used in manufacturing of plastic bags also contaminate the food stuffs.

With increasing consumption of plastic, generation of plastic waste is also growing tremendously in the city. Amongst the variety of things, plastic bags are seen as a big pollutant in the city

Plastic bags find their origin in a variety of places. Non-grocery retail stores and restaurants are significant contributors, but there is no greater impact than the plastic bag waste that is generated by grocery stores. Due to this fact, grocery stores have been targeted as the major venue in reducing plastic bag use

This phenomenon had been overlooked until the last decade when cities around the world slowly started recognizing the patterns and regulating the then unlimited usage and overconsumption of plastic bags by businesses and shoppers.

India's plastics consumption is one of the highest in the world. Yet, very little has been done to recycle, re-use and dispose of plastic waste. Cities and countries in Europe were first to introduce regulatory legislation of plastic bags usage. According to the Central Government of India rules of the Law, manufacture, storage, sale/ use of plastic carry bags having less than 20 microns i.e. equivalent to 0.2mm thickness is restricted. In order to bring this in effect, an amendment on plastic bags was issued in 2003, according to which MoEFCC prohibited the manufacture, sale and use of carry bags below the size of 8” x 12”, retaining the 20 microns thickness restriction.

Reactions to the ban have so far been mixed. While most citizens believe it's a good idea to ban plastic bags, shopkeepers are not very pleased. They say it will become difficult for them to sell their products as most people specifically ask for plastic bags in which to carry their purchases. Meanwhile Arvind Mehta, managing committee member of the All India Plastic Manufacturers Association, says: "More than 1,000 manufacturing plants will be forced to shut down in the state, putting 100,000 people out of work," once the ban comes into effect. Mumbai alone suffered losses of around Rs 4,000 crore, including damage to property, in the recent flooding, which also had its effect on public health. Urban planners and environment activists identified plastic bags as one of the main factors leading to waterlogging in the city. (*The Guardian*, 2005 AP, 2005)

Recently, the government notified the Plastic Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2011, to replace the earlier Recycled Plastics Manufacture and Usage Rules, 2003, towards better management of plastic waste. According to the new rules, the minimum thickness of plastic bags has been raised to 40 microns and recycled carry bags made from compostable plastics need to conform to specific Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) norms. The ban on plastic carry bags less than 50 microns in thickness came into effect on February 24th 2015 in Maharashtra and the state Environment Minister Ramdas Kadam announced strict punishments to force compliance. The penalty on sale and manufacture of bags not meeting the allowed specifications would be Rs. 1-5 lakh and may entail imprisonment up to 5 years, according to a press release from the minister. Officials from the Maharashtra Pollution

Control Board (MPCB) said the ban was effective earlier but implementation was poor. The Brihanmumbai Municipal Corporation had been making concerted efforts to impose the ban since 2010(Indian express) .

To solve problems caused by plastics, new technologies are being piloted which include tracking trash through frequency identification (RFID) tags and cellular transmitters, having citizens track plastic debris using their smartphones, using drones or barriers to collect plastic debris, and turning plastics back into fuel.

The different waste-reduction strategies are Recycling , Reduction in material use through product reuse, and Reduce the use of plastic by switching to other alternative biodegradable materials like cloth , jute , paper etc. and energy recovery as fuel .

Use of alternative biodegradable materials is being focused here as we want to generate alternative income opportunity for BOP of Vimannagar by making cloth or paper bags and supplying to the traders and residents of Vimannagar as part of Social Entrepreneurship endeavor and in the process make Vimannagar plastic free locality as part of Environmental cleansing effort . This will help in sustainability drive.

Methodology:

Secondary Research

Secondary research comprised collecting documents relating to the waste generation, plastic Industry, regulations etc. from the varied sources in the public domain. The following aspects were covered in the secondary research:

- Regulatory framework in the chosen areas for the plastic industry and in particular plastic bags
- Current status of waste generation in the city
- Current scenario of the plastic industry

Primary Research

The study included both qualitative and quantitative research. Survey was conducted to collate information from around 120 target audience- retailers / vendors and consumers. On the basis of the literature review and secondary research, a survey questionnaire was designed for vendors and consumers, to get information on consumption of plastic bags in the locality

and the effectiveness of this restriction. Various parks, shopping malls, government and non - government offices, were also visited during the field study.

The present study used tools like simple percentage .

Limitation of the study

Due to resource constraints and limited access to information, it was difficult to have a large Sample size. Also, vendors and retailers were reluctant in sharing information. We did not have any means to verify plastic carry bag quality (in terms of microns) during the survey, hence had to rely on our observation and information provided by the local vendors.

Findings & Discussion:

Table 1 : Demographic factors of the respondents

Demographic factor	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Gender		
Male	88	76.52
Female	27	23.47
Total	115	100
Age (in years)		
Below 25	26	22.61
25-35	43	37.39
Above 35	46	40.00
Total	115	100
Category		
Retailers	94	81.74
Residents	21	18.26
Total	115	100

It was inferred that 88 percent of the respondents were male. 40 percent of the respondents belong to the age group above 35 years. 81.74 percent of the respondents were retailers in this study.

Table 2 : Awareness of hazardous effects of plastic

Awareness	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	81	70.43
No	34	29.56
Total	115	100

Out of 115 respondents , 70.43 percent of the respondents were aware about the hazardous effects of plastic and 29.56 percent had responded negatively.

Table 3 : Usage of Plastic bags

Usage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	83	72.17
No	32	27.83
Total	115	100

72.17 percent of the respondents accepted that they use plastic bags but only 27.83percent stated that they do not use plastic bags.

Table 4 : Reasons for Using plastic bags

Reasons	No. of Responses	No. of Respondents	Percentage of responses
Durable	36		40.44
Inexpensive	39		43.82
Lighter Weight	21		23.59
Better Safety &hygiene	10		11.2
Extreme thermal & Insulation properties	0		0
No other alternative available	23		25.84
No responses	26		
Total		115-26=89	

Table 5 : Interest in shifting to alternatives of plastic

Reasons	No. of Responses	No. of Respondents	Percentage of responses
Cloth bag	51		44.34
Jute bag	27		23.47
Paper bag	50		43.47
No responses	20		17.39
Total		115-20=95	

Table 6 : Charge for plastic bags

Charges	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	27	23.47
No	81	70.43
No response	7	6.08
Total	115	100

Majority 81 percent of the respondents give (or get) plastic bags for free . 27 percent of the respondents stated that they charge for (retailers) or buy (consumers) plastic bags ..

Table 7 : Readiness to shift to Eco-friendly non -woven cloth bags

Charges	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	67	58.26
No	40	34.78
No response	8	6.95
Total	115	100

Among 115 respondents , majority 58.26 percent were ready to shift to eco-friendly non-woven cloth bags .

Table 8 : Expectation of the prices of cloth bags

Charges	No. of Respondents	Percentage
50 p- Re. 1	28	24.34
Re. 1 – Rs.. 2	63	54.78
No idea/ 2-10	24	20.87
Total	115	100

Out of 115 respondents , 54.78 percent expected the price of average sized cloth bags to be in the range of Re. 1- Rs. 2. . 24. 34 percent of respondents thinks it to be cheaper between 50 p – Re. 1 per bag . 20.87 percent had no idea about their price.

Table 9 : Readiness to place order of cloth bags by retailers

Placing order	No.of Respondents(retailers)	Percentage
Yes	40	42.55
No	48	51.06
No response	6	6.38
Total	94	100

Out of 94 respondents (retailers) , 42.55 placed order initial order for plastic bags . 51 percent were not at all interested to do so. 6.38 percent chose not to respond..

Other findings from the Study :

1. Shockingly, most of the respondents believe that government does not take any real steps in controlling the usage of plastic bags. According to people, the government has not been taking any visible measures to reduce the use of plastic .The most common measure the government has taken is raiding shops and charging to the extent of 10,000/- from small vendors if caught using plastic bags..
2. The previous ban on plastic bags did not reduce the usage of the plastic, but it was only helpful for the large companies to earn money by charging the customers for the bags .
3. Most of the traders believe that if government really wants to reduce the usage of plastic bags, they need to ban the industries which are producing the bags in turn banning the products.
4. Most of the shops use around 20-50 plastic bags a day.
5. Most of the respondents are ready to use the cloth bag or any other alternative to plastic bag given the product is cheaper or equal to the plastic bags.
6. More than 2500 orders of cloth bags were raised by the student data collectors from the respondent retailers..

Practical Application / Value: The study was carried out to assess the readiness and need of plastic alternatives in the Vimannagar locality. This need can be exploited to make commercially successful biodegradable alternatives by the local underprivileged women, thereby facilitating them to earn a living in a sustainable manner.

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